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Effects of cross-stream rotor spacing on dual-rotor axial-flow marine turbine performance

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Abstract

In current-drive marine energy applications, some deployment strategies explore mounting multiple axial-flow rotors from a single platform. The rotor and nacelle for each turbine unit can be deployed from bottom mounted foundations and towers, or from floating platforms where the system is lowered into the flow to harness energy. This project explores the potential impact on rotor power performance of a scaled current-driven marine turbine through the implementation of high-resolution 3D unsteady computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The turbine studied is an axial-flow, two-bladed marine turbine with counter rotating rotors, each with a rotor diameter of $d_T = 0.5$ m, representing approximately a 1:40 scale system. This study is based on the U.S. Department of Energy's Reference Model 1 tidal current turbine and uses laboratory flume experimental data for validating numerical results. A transient $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model and sliding mesh technique was used to model the inflow and wake dynamics on the full 3D device geometry at multiple tip-speed ratios. Three distinct lateral rotor separations are studied to understand to what extent rotor hydrodynamic efficiency is impacted, including rotor center spacings of $1.2 d_T$, $1.4 d_T$, and $1.6 d_T$. The numerical model implemented showed a good correlation of turbine performance to experimental measurements for all tip-speed ratios studied, validating the numerical results for power estimation, and demonstrating the advantages of this model when dealing with complex flow dynamics around marine turbine rotors. Results showed a tendency for higher power production as the rotors are spaced farther apart, with an increase in the coefficient of performance of approximate $C_p = +3.7\%$ compared to the base scenario ($1.4 d_T$ rotor spacing). Results are presented in relevance to the structural support and economic implications for systems where multiple rotors are deployed from a single support structure.